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USING CULTURALLY SIGNIFICANT PRECEDENT NAMES IN NEWSPAPER HEADLINES

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ГАЗЕТ ТАҚЫРЫПАТТАРЫНДАҒЫ МӘДЕНИ МӘНДІ ПРЕЦЕДЕНТТІ ЕСІМДЕРДІҢ ҚОЛДАНЫСЫ

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Introduction. Title of headline is the name that is given depending on the content of the information from the text. At the same time, it should attract the reader's attention and lead them to read the text. Even the idea, which expressed in the text is in the core of the title. It is possible to predict the thought that will be expressed in the text, to form a point of view through the title. Certainly, it should do with the skill of subject. Finally, we should not magnify if we say that there is a responsibility to arouse public consciousness in the title.

The author can express his point of view through a headline in the newspaper genre, if it is explicitly or implicitly. For example, "The operational investigation team tried to arrest Mr. Zhomart Yertayev" (AT. 01.07.2015), as well as "run away, the banker ran away" (ZhA. 02.07.2018). These articles raise one topic. The former chairman of "Alliance Bank" Zh.Ertayev, who was accused of pocketing a non-refundable loan and causing losses to the bank's funds, said that he escaped from the operational and investigative team. However, even from the name of the two titles and more can be seen.

The first topic is neutral, that conveys information about this situation and has occurred, while the second topic is made on sarcasm. Using speech, sarcasm, characteristic of children, it conveys their irresponsibility (K.Yergaliev, E.Asanbayeva, 2015). At the same time, the foreign scientist W. Rivers of "The Mass Media: Reporting, Writing, Editing" emphasizes the following tasks of the newspaper headline:

- 1) to attract the reader's attention;
- 2) to deliver the basic essence and content of the text;
- 3) to give a symbolic name
- 4) to make the newspaper more attractive (Rivers W., 1990).

The activities of newspaper headlines can be divided into elementary and secondary. The main function of a newspaper headline is, first of all, to provide small and urgent information about a newspaper headline (this is the information, content service of the headline (K.Yergaliev, K.Tekganov, E.Asanbayeva, 2014). Scientist V. I. Konkov "The title of the work should convey its content-idea to a certain extent. If the newspaper headline does not meet its task, there is a probability that the newspaper material will not find its reader and affect the reader (Konkov V., 1995). Also it shows, how much the headline of the newspaper makes sense in drawing the reader's attention to the text.

There is a huge load of the topic, which serves to attract the attention of the reader and influence. At that time, precedent names also have a special function in the creation of an impressive and the relevant topic that adds meaning to the text and serves as a basis for thought. The history of the use of pretentious names in the Kazakh word culture begins far beyond. Even before the appearance of the Kazakh press, examples of literary language is the art of oral speeches, that were examples of speech with precedent names in samples of eloquence. This is a culture and tradition of Kazakh speech, which aims to pass the good that loves and humiliate the bad. The use of precedent names in the press dates back to the XIX century, when the first Kazakh Press began to appear. The structure of precedent names used according to the requirements of life in different eras, the approach of the times is different. We will focus on the use of precedent names in the article on the pages of post-independence newspapers.

The concept of a precedent name began to be used widely in Kazakh linguistics after independence. Especially, a very good idea is given about the use of precedent names on the pages of the press in the works of the

scientist N. Ualiyev. The purpose of the use of such precedent names in the language of the scientist press is to provide a special way of influence the consciousness of the country, usual to the memorized word. Such words include legendary stories, proverbs and sayings. For example, “the word in the basket of Kozhanasyr”, “stories in the turban of Tazsha Bala” are the most used precedent word models on the Kazakh radio (Uali N., 2007).

The term precedent (in Latin – praecedent) is a concept that refers to a situation in which truth is a model or allusion to situations that have already occurred in life, as well as later ones. One of the important tasks of the author is to address of the newspaper text to the reader, such as addressee is to evoke emotions, influence public consciousness. It is called a pragmatic position in scientific language. The activity of the addressee to influence the reader’s consciousness is divided by scientists:

- 1) informational;
- 2) phatic (attracting the reader’s attention),
- 3) manipulative position (forming a point of view).

A precedent situation is a situation that has taken place in the history of a particular society and has an instructive example for generations. A precedent text is the result of completed thinking, speech activity. Such a text includes word samples of a legendary story, poem, literary work, etc.

The use of precedent names in newspaper headlines enhances its figurative nature. It increases the likelihood of acceptance. Such names find to use associated with certain precedent texts. For example, how to touch is the description of the novel “Oh, the world of genius” by the poet and writer M. Shair through the title “How impressive is the description of “Today’s Don Kikhote?” (EK. 28.11.2006). As well as, the title “The True Hercules of the Kazakh spirit” is an impressive reflection in the book of Academician M. Zholdasbekov (ZhA. 01.03.2001) (K.Yessenova, 2007).

The concept of “precedent” in the last years of the XX century by Russian linguistics is considered in the works of Yu.N.Karaulov, Yu. A.Sorokin, while the phrase “precedent name” began to rise in the studies of such Russian scientists like V.V. Krasnykh, D.B. Gudkov, O.A. Vorozhtsova, E.L. Berezovich, G.G. Sergeeva, O.S. Boyarskikh. And the introduction of this concept into Kazakh linguistics also coincides with this period. More precisely, the term precedent in Russian linguistics was introduced into Russian linguistics by the Russian scientist Yu.N.Karaulov in 1986 (Karaulov Yu., 1987).

It is worth to note the names of such scientists as T. Zhanuzak, T. Konyrov, E. Kerimbayev, who were the first to comment on this issue, although they did not use the term precedent in Kazakh linguistics. For example. T. Zhanuzak puts forward a historical and cognitive problem that corresponds to the theory of one name or one concept. Shyghaybay is a symbol measure of a stingy person, Asan is a very sad soul, Kodar is a merciless, cruel, Kose is a symbol dishonest in the Kazakh sense, (Imanberdieva S., 2015).

The scientist N. Tairova considers precedent names as a special object of study in the work, which functioned of precedent texts in Russian and Kazakh newspapers (Tairova N., 2015). Scientists, who studied specifically the pragmatic activities of newspaper headlines of K. Yergaliyev., E. Asanbaeva’s in the work’s of pragmatic activities of newspaper headlines emphasize the specifics and importance of using precedent names for headlines (Yergalieva K., Asanbaeva E., 2015).

To conclude, it is not without pragmatics of influence in the population for the purpose of using precedent names in the language of the press. In particular, precedent names are particular importance to increase the influence of the Press in the consciousness of the population.

Materials and methods. The use of precedent names in the media language, especially, there are two different stylistic purposes in newspaper headlines: first, the word (precedent name), which is the basis for a familiar topic from the culture or history of the country, and it comes to the reader’s attention immediately. Such a title will encourage the reader to read the article. For this reason, a communicative connection is established between the reader and the author. This is what caused various thoughts in the reader’s mind: “what did the author mean when he used this word?”, “this word would have come from this story, which I know” creates an internal dialogue of criticism. In the minds of the reader, who has fallen into such an inner wave of thought before to read the article, the likelihood of believe, accepting the information in the text of increases (Takehiko Y., 2001).

A precedent name is a historical event that influenced the emergence of this word, serves as a bridge between the memory of the situation and this situation that takes place today. More precisely, it contributes to the rapid perception of familiar information, regardless of the current situation. Thus, an associative chain is born in the reader’s cognition and a semantic space is established (Sanjay S., 2014).

The ability of precedent texts, full of content that can attract the attention of the public, is an indispensable tool for newspaper headlines that keep the reader’s attention in the spotlight. For example, “winter is long in our side”. The basis for this precedent name is the story of the famous writer O. Bokey “winter on our side is long”. When the journalist who founded the conversation put the title of his article “winter is long on our side” (HSE, 20.10.2019).

It was intended to draw the reader’s attention to the impressive description of the flood in the Tarbagatai District of the East Kazakhstan region. Also, the writer M. Auezov gives a feeling of disgust to the 13-year-old girl Gaziza in the story “the day of the defenseless”, who was subjected to violence, abuse and the tragic fate that ended in death. It is when this “day of the defenseless» becomes the headline of the newspaper that the public consciousness, to remember the fate of Gaziza, takes pity on the fate of the baby, which sold abroad and feels the need to stop (AT. 02.12.2017).

Karaulov Yu.N. gave the following definition of the term precedent: “we mean a linguistic unit, it is the

texts, that can have an emotional and cognitive impact on a particular person with the aim of referring to similar situations in each era as well as in the public environment surrounding of him" (Karaulov Yu., 1987). Along with Y. N. Karaulov, I.V.Bagaeva, V.V.Krasnykh, D.B.Gudkov, I.V.Zakharenko, who touched about this topic, which emphasized that the term precedent is a very broad concept and proposed to divide it into 4 parts:

1. precedent name
2. precedent pronunciation
3. precedent text
4. the precedent situation (Krasnykh V.V, Gudkov D.B, Zakharenko I.V, Bagaeva I.V, 1997).

Among the four different precedent structures mentioned, the one, that finds the most usage is the precedent pronunciation. Stable phrases, verses, proverbs belonging to precedent pronunciation are very convenient to present as a subject "ready-made template" are structures. For example, "the same rock is one rock" (SS. – 06/27/2018), "the letter of the scientist does not die..." (SS. – 18.05.2021), "It will be added to the blanket of the city administration" (Ja. – 09.09.2019), "A younger brother grows by looking at his elder brother" (SS. – 13.05.2016).

The practice of "fragmentary use" of subjects, that come to present the initial part to the subject and apply the second part is also often encountered with precedent utterances. The goal is to increase the effect, to over-clock the thought. "The fifth wheel of the cart: Are those with hip piercings still enjoying a soft pillow?" (ZhA. – 16.08.2021), "Again about Arkankergen and Aksai Gorge or "Achilles' heel" (ZhA. – 11.09.2021) (Yergalieva K., Asanbayeva E., 2015).

The headlines of newspapers made of precedent pronunciations can be divided into two: precedent pronunciations that have undergone changes, which used without any changes. However, changing precedent pronunciations have little effect on readers. This is because the minds of the people tend to accept the unchanged version of precedent pronunciations. However, in the language of newspapers, there is often a modified use of the idea that the reader wants to express in accordance with the content of the article. This is due to the activity of the newspaper to influence the reader (Dinee S., 2013).

The scientist G. K. Ihsangalieva divides the methods of "change" of modified precedent texts into three types: quantifiable, qualificative, mixed types. In the quantifiable form, one sentence in the composition of a precedent text is replaced by another word or another word is inserted. According to the qualitatv approach, not a whole particle in a precedent text is subject to phonetic, that is, alphabetic changes. Well, in the mixed approach, this approach is used alternately (Ihsangalieva G., 2000).

The Russian scientist S. I. Smetanina deeply studies the use of precedent texts within a journalistic text, highlighting several types of ways to include precedent phenomena in the "media text". "Text A is another author's, "text B" is his own (author of the article) (Smetanina S., 2002).

1) text A is equivalent to text B: "if you want to be a country, fix your cradle" (HSE. 13.01.2021), "if your name does not come up, burn the Earth" (horse. 12.07.2018), "there is no insult in caution" (P. 2001 No. 7). Text A is related to text B semantically and is used as a subject without any changes. On the basis of the same background, the author's own idea is text, which is given. In this case, the citation of the title is enclosed in quotation marks.

2) an example of a text that is equivalent to text A and text B: "What makes you thirsty, quench your thirst" (P. 2017. No. 4), "An eagle goes hunting in Kansonar..." (P. 2006 No.9). In these examples, the reporter expresses through quotes that the subject is not his own.

3) text A is the basis for writing text B. In this approach, intertext communication is very complex: text A is a fragment of text A is text B.

3.1. to short the text and add a new meaning to it: "The bullet fired by the father" (HSE. 08.06.2012). If the full version of this proverb is based on the upbringing that parents give to the child, then the first part of it is taken for the title. In the end, we can find out that the article is talking about the place of the father in raising children. In addition, in these articles, only parts of the precedent texts are taken. "When the girl grows up, the beauty of the country" (P. 2013. No. 4). In fact, this is the full version of the proverb: "If a girl grows, the beauty of the country, if flowers grow, the beauty of the Earth". In the same way, the use of the proverb "A good name will never die, a scholar's letter will never die" is widely used in the press. For example, an article about the Republican scientific conference dedicated to the memory of a historical scientist, Professor, academician T. S. Sadykov was called "the letter of a scientist does not die" (SS. 18.05.2010).

3.2. Disclosure of the meaning with the addition of the text. For example, it is known that during the period of December events, the phrase "you have broken the hearts of young people, December" was formed in the mouth of the people. And now the article, which touched upon the fate of the girls who took part in the December events, is guided by this precedent name. In particular, the phrase "You broke the girls' hearts, December!" changes to. (SS. 28.11.1996). Also in the vernacular there is the phrase "health is a great wealth". He draws the attention of the public by creating the basis for the title of an article describing the situation of a people who are negligent in maintaining public health and expresses the soul: "we say that health is a great wealth" (HSE. 02.11.2019).

3.3. Situational, alternating use of words depending on the purpose of the topic. For example, changing the popular proverb "Where there is a ditch, there is water, and where there is water, there is water" to "Where there is death, there is mourning" and presenting it in the title can attract the reader's attention (HSE. 26.11.2012). The phrase "Oyan, Kazakh" (the theme of the poem) by M. Dulatov, known to six Alash, is used skillfully in the title of the article by the correspondent, who spoke about the good results of the summit in Astana: "Kuan, Kazakh!" (HSE. 20.10.2010).

If you have a midday life, folk wisdom calling for the day's cattle collection "take care of winter in summer!" I mean, six months of winter and summer. All Kazakhs are used to do this. It was very successful to test the Heat Transfer Center, which showed that when winter came, it could not add to heat the housing, and even showed that it was not ready for it, and the title of the exposing article changed this precedent: "summer your winter sleigh!"

Research results. The title of the article, which implies that the governors and who did not elect the winter sleigh in the summer, also which will now receive their punishment in December and demonstrates the irresponsibility of the governors for the situation that torments the country (HSE. 24.09.2010). In conclusion, the title of the article was used purposefully to demonstrate the powerful position of the head of government, who puts this issue before the governors.

Many of the precedent names that form the basis of newspaper headlines are taken from versions that have a public meaning. For example, the use of Abai's poems "we study in a boarding school, many Kazakh children" as "we study in construction, many Kazakh children" increases the expressive tone of the article (HSE. – 13.04.2021). In general, it is common for verses in Kazakh poetry to be included in newspaper headlines as a precedent name. For example, "Ayagoz, where are you going?" (D. Babatayevich), "Kerey, where are you going?" (Bukhar zhyrau) poem "Yrys, where are you going?" (P. 2004 №4), "Media, where are you going?" (HSE. 18.03.2021), "history, where are you going?" (HSE. 10.10.2017), which became the basis for many newspaper headlines.

The next approach found in using precedent names as article titles is to complicate the article title by supplementing precedent names with words. For example, "Male and female: will the rights of two halves and one whole be equal?" (HSE. 18.11.2016). "Will the hostage be retaliated against?" (HSE 21.05.2021).

The title has an informative, naming, pragmatic function. The name function of the title in the newspaper informs the information and the function of evaluating the event in the text is observed. The informational function of the topic is unique in the concise, visual, and also impressive presentation of the thought expressed in the text. It is considered a communicative function of the topic. In this way, the topic, performing an informative function, affects the reader's knowledge. As a result, the topic forms a conceptual-thematic network and serves as an analysis and explanation, to convey the idea and content of the text through language units (Tereszkiewicz A., 2012).

The subject acts as a (pragmatic) influence on the reader and contributes to the reader's good perception of the text, performing secondary tasks. Such sub-services of the topic include evaluative value, graphic interpretation, advertising, integrative services (Seib P., 1997). While this main service includes a constant feature in relation to the text of any newspaper, secondary service can be reflected in different levels in each text. In understanding the meaning of the topic in the newspaper, the knowledge of the reader is very important.

For example, "Secret like his sister-in-law" (EQ. 06.03.04).

Although this topic seems familiar (jenge is one of the Kazakh family names. It means to express one's thoughts without bending and the close relationship between like-minded and close people), it is not known what content it refers to in this text. That is, what conditions were the basis for choosing the topic, it becomes clear only after reading the entire text.

According to the upbringing in a Kazakh family, where one sees one's sister-in-law as a mother, one cannot hide any secrets from her. Therefore, it is clear that there is an open conversation between the characters in this popular article. Here, such a familiar theme from the folk culture to the life of the country will have a special effect on the reader. In the reader's mind, it creates an association with such concepts as "friendship", "compassion", "care", which increases the reader's interest in reading the text of the article. We can see that the theme is connected based on the nature of the action described in the text.

Expressive, evaluative tone, playful, figurative topics have a high potential to influence the reader. Such headlines inform the reader about the content of the newspaper and influence the perception. (Morley J., 1998) In addition to the precedent names that have such an impact on the society, it was noticed that there are more contrasting topics in the modern Kazakh press. It is observed that modern newspaper titles are developed in terms of information and impact on the reader. (Jarumul D., 1991)

The evaluative character is reflected in its expressive and emotional tone. In other words, it becomes a tradition to use words of national cultural significance in modern press materials in order to encourage and "power" the reader to study the newspaper text. For example, "If you're safe, you'll be safe" (Allah preserves those who are cautious), (EQ. 22.05.04); "To swallow a camel was a light diet" (JA. 22.11.15), "Each singer is boiling in his own cauldron" (JA. 01.01.14), "A smiling boy is good for a laugh" (ZhA. 22.11.17) etc.

Newspaper headlines always aim to influence the reader. Its system of cognitive to think is based on elementary knowledge. As a result, it becomes the main pillar of the position of the organizing team, which forms a whole newspaper.

It is not a matter of fact that the themes are taken from poems of poets familiar to the reader. Its impact on the reader will increase. Especially, such newspaper headlines are often taken from precedent names. This shows the strength of the pragmatic potential of precedent names in our language for the reader. There are three types of its creation:

1) Allusion. It defines the names of prose and poetry works. For example, "Khamit who chased the gang" (JA. 01.08.19), "Which way will you become a brick?" (T. 08.08.19)

2) Allusions in the name of movies. "Intertwined destinies" (EQ. 30.06.18), "The rich people also cry" (EK. 12.24.15).

3) The names of songs, anthems and popular works as titles. For example, "Almaty is the capital city" (AZ. 17.12.15), "Love is an eternal fairy tale"

(AZ. 17.01.14), “Goodbye, Sandro, see you soon...” (AZ. 27.12.05).

After all, predicate nouns are linguistic units, that can affect a certain person emotionally and cognitively. Precedent linguistic units are words that affect a person from a cognitive and emotional point of view. It is words familiar to the person and its surroundings (Evans H., 1974).

In relation to this issue, scientist S. Imanberdieva prefers to use the term *logoepisteme* highlighted by G. Kostomarov and N. Burvikova in her scientific article “Transformation of *logoepistemes* in mass media” (Imanberdieva S., Egizbaeva N., 2015).

Logoepistema is very extensive in terms of knowledge and information. In this regard, the author can add the values, according to his position. *Logoepisteme* is one of the most effective methods that interest the reader today. We can call this a method that has penetrated intensively into the Kazakh press and began to show its results.

Logoepistema is a new, surprising method by nature (Simon-Vanderbergen A.M., 1981). Therefore, it is easy for the reader to accept. Although it is playful, it has a significant pragmatic load. In this way, it not only fulfills the role of playfulness, but also performs an evaluative function. Finally, the following conclusions can be drawn about *logoepisteme*:

Firstly, *logoepisteme* is an indicator of the author’s position. How the journalist evaluates the issue can be seen from the headlines, which are already familiar to the masses;

Secondly, the *logoepisteme* acts as a bridge between the author and the reader. Such precedent names, which are an indicator of national identity specific to a certain culture and are unique from newspaper materials.

Thirdly, any *logoepistemic* use demonstrates the journalist’s skill to use the vocabulary and the desire for innovation.

Discussions. In the process of working on the topic, there was a need to determine the level of influence of precedent names on young people. At the same time, “what is the influence of precedent names to read the text?” a survey was conducted among students on the topic:

During the questionnaire, respondents were asked 5 questions. In particular, 97 (64.6%) of them are respondents from 18 to 23. The survey involved 85 (90%) women and (10%) 15 men.

Do you know what titles are made up of the first “precedent names”? “80 respondents said ‘yes’ and 20 respondents said ‘no’.

“Can titles consist of precedent names pay attention to themselves and create an internal dialogue within the reader? “75 respondents said yes” and “25 respondents said no”.

“Is there an immediate interest in reading when you see headlines made up of precedent names?”. ‘85 respondents said yes’ and ‘25 respondents said no’.

“Were there any points where the headlines made up of precedent names contributed to your point of view and prompted you to change your decision?”. ‘75 respondents said yes, and 25 respondents said no’.

“Does the purpose of headings usage to make up of precedent names to think?” ‘70 respondents said yes and 30 respondents said no’.

As a result of the questionnaire, it was found that topics consist of precedent names actually have an impact in the minds of young people. The main task, which face the headline of the newspaper is to influence the reader’s mind, to motivate him to form a point of view. And in a result, it is proved how effective is to use precedent names as newspaper headlines.

Reporter-scientist N. Uali’s conclusion as a result of his research can be compared with the results of the survey. According to the scientist, precedent names enrich the press text with emotional meaning. It shows the dimension of internal culture characteristic of a journalist, forms an image (Uali N., 2007). We can see from the results of the questionnaire how much the headings consisting of precedent nouns affect the reader’s cognition and encourage them to read the text itself.

Conclusions. The title to the text of the newspaper is not only a function of the title of the content of the article, but also the essence of the game, professional position and attitude that the author would like to express through this article. From this point of view, newspaper topics have a very high ability to push society. The study and recognition of this task of the newspaper theme observed in the course of the experiment is relevant in any era.

The purpose of the article is, as a result of scientific research, to determine the precedent task of newspaper headlines, which contributes to the formation and development of national consciousness, influencing public consciousness.

The theme of the newspaper involves, first of all, attracting the attention of the reader. Also, giving the article a symbolic title, increases the attractiveness of the newspaper. At the same time, newspaper headlines containing precedent names have a very high potential for impact, increasing the pictorial nature. In order to differentiate scientific works on newspaper topics containing case names, to generalize the theoretical concept, conclusion and its practical study, it was proved as a result of the survey that case newspaper headlines are linguistic means that have a special impact on public consciousness.

The question raised in the article was analyzed from the point of view of the pragmatics. In the course of the study, the questions of questioning students were considered from the point of view of a pragmatic position, and were not based on theoretical questions. As a result of the survey, it was proved that scientific results, in fact, have the ability of newspaper headlines to influence public opinion. The results of the survey showed that the precedent newspaper topics are a potential force for influencing, exciting, and influencing the public consciousness.

The activity of newspaper headlines, which consisting of precedent names, to form a public opinion is always very important. After all, newspaper headlines have a special place in increasing the readability of articles and texts become a driving force for national consciousness.

Newspaper headlines with a precedent name are a value that can contribute to the formation of the national identity and integrity of today's society, convey cultural and historical information. Therefore, especially, it is relevant to analyze the professional skills of journalists who reproduce precedent words with their modified use through scientific research. Such researches demonstrate, firstly, the function of precedent names in the formation of public consciousness, and secondly, the style of the press is the power of the literary language.

Newspaper headlines consisting of precedent names are an indispensable tool for influencing and arousing interest in the reader's mind. The specifics of the formation of headings were analyzed on the basis of examples, which is formed in using precedent names in this article. The pragmatic meaning of precedent names in the style of the press is revealed.

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